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Background: Cancer therapy-related heart failure (CTHF) is a major complication of modern oncologic treatments, particularly in breast cancer patients exposed to anthracyclines and HER2-targeted therapies. While long-term outcomes have been described, data on acute in-hospital outcomes remain limited.

Purpose: To evaluate in-hospital outcomes of CTHF compared with non-cancer-related heart failure (NCTHF) in patients with prior breast cancer.

Methods: We analyzed the National Inpatient Sample (2016–2021) to identify adult female patients with a history of breast cancer hospitalized with acute heart failure. Patients were stratified into CTHF and NCTHF groups. Multivariable logistic regression was performed to adjust for comorbidities and demographic differences.

Results: A total of 47,300 hospitalizations were included, of which 1,920 (4.1%) had CTHF. Patients with CTHF were younger (mean age 76 vs 60 years) and had lower rates of hypertension, chronic kidney disease, atrial fibrillation, coronary artery disease, and diabetes (all $p < 0.05$). Despite this, CTHF was associated with significantly worse outcomes, including higher in-hospital mortality, cardiogenic shock, acute kidney and liver injury, and increased need for mechanical circulatory support (all $p < 0.001$). Length of stay was longer in the CTHF group (6 vs 5 days; $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Among breast cancer patients hospitalized with heart failure, cancer therapy-related heart failure is associated with significantly worse in-hospital outcomes despite a lower burden of traditional cardiovascular risk factors. These findings highlight the aggressive clinical course of CTHF and underscore the need for early recognition and specialized management strategies.